

Diversity and spatial distribution of the gastropod fauna (Mollusca: Gastropoda) on subtidal sedimentary substrata of the Ensenada de Baiona (Galicia, NW Iberian Peninsula)

Diversidad y distribución espacial de la fauna de gasterópodos (Mollusca: Gastropoda) de los sustratos sedimentarios submareales de la Ensenada de Baiona (Galicia, NW Península Ibérica)

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ABSTRACT

Gastropods (Mollusca: Gastropoda) are an important component of soft-bottom faunas in temperate latitudes. The diversity and distribution of gastropod fauna on sedimentary substrata at the Ensenada de Baiona (Galicia, NW Iberian Peninsula) was studied by means of quantitative sampling. The total number of species was similar to that found in other Galician "rias" dominated by sandy sediments and greater than in other "rias" whose sediments are mostly muddy. Gastropod assemblages in gravelly and sandy bottoms of the inlet were, in general, more diverse than those in muddy sediments.

The distribution and composition of gastropod assemblages in the Ensenada de Baiona is related to the granulometric composition and median grain size of the sediment, which are, in turn, influenced by the intrinsic hydrodynamic conditions of the inlet. These patterns of gastropod distribution are similar to those previously reported for other benthic taxa in the same area.

RESUMEN

Los moluscos gasterópodos (Mollusca: Gastropoda) constituyen un importante componente de la fauna de fondos blandos en latitudes templadas. La diversidad y distribución de la fauna de gasterópodos de los sustratos sedimentarios de la ensenada de Baiona (Galicia, NW península Ibérica) fue estudiada por medio de muestras cuantitativas. El número total de especies encontrado en la ensenada fue similar al registrado en otras rías de Galicia caracterizadas por presentar sedimentos principalmente arenosos, y mayor que en las rías dominadas por sedimentos fangosos. La distribución y composición de las comunidades de gasterópodos en la ensenada de Baiona está relacionada con la composición granulométrica y la mediana del tamaño de grano del sedimento, que están determinadas a su vez por las particulares condiciones hidrodinámicas de la zona. Estos patrones de distribución son similares a los registrados para otros grupos zoológicos en esta misma ensenada.

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INTRODUCTION

Benthic faunas inhabiting subtidal soft-bottoms are influenced by a number of interacting abiotic and biotic factors, such as granulometry, hydrodynamism, organic matter content, predation and competition (see, for example, WILDISH, 1977; GRAY, 1981; WILSON, 1991). Spatio-temporal fluctuations of those factors determine, in many cases, the patterns of distribution and composition of benthic assemblages (STUBBLEFIELD, PERMENTER AND SWIFT, 1977). The characterization of those patterns is of paramount importance to evaluate the relative role of natural perturbances and of that derived from anthropogenic activities (UNDERWOOD, 1992).

The Galician rias (NW Spain) have highly diverse benthic faunas due, in part, to the great variety of habitats and sediments present there (p.e. LÓPEZ-JAMAR, 1981; MORA, 1982; TRONCOSO AND URGORRI, 1993). The seashore around the rias is highly populated and therefore subjected to many perturbations such as those due to the culture of bivalves on rafts, construction of harbour facilities, industrial activities and disposal of sewages (LÓPEZ-JAMAR, 1978; LÓPEZ-JAMAR, GONZÁLEZ AND MEJUTO, 1986; CASTELLANOS, HERNÁNDEZ-VEGA AND JUNOY, 2003). The effects of these perturbations mostly translate into organic enrichment and changes in sedimentary composition (LÓPEZ-JAMAR, 1978; LÓPEZ-JAMAR AND MEJUTO, 1985), which, in turn, affect the composition of benthic assemblages and the stability of the populations of many species (LÓPEZ-JAMAR *ET AL.*, 1986).

There are still many areas of the Galician rias whose benthic fauna is little known, such as the Ensenada de Baiona, an inlet located to the south of the Ría de Vigo. Mollusca are an important component of soft-bottom benthic faunas (TRONCOSO AND URGORRI, 1993; GUERRA-GARCÍA AND GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, 2004) and their study might be also useful to check the state of benthic assemblages (BOENING, 1999). Lists of species of the molluscan fauna present

in the Ensenada de Baiona were provided by MACANDREW (1849), HIDALGO (1886), ROLÁN (1983) and ROLÁN, OTERO AND ROLÁN-ÁLVAREZ (1989); MOREIRA, QUINTAS AND TRONCOSO (2005) studied the distribution of subtidal molluscan assemblages as a whole. Nevertheless, the composition and distribution of subtidal gastropod assemblages as such have not been described from this area yet. In fact, the description of gastropod assemblages has often been neglected in papers dealing with soft-bottom mollusc faunas. In general, more attention is paid to bivalves which are, on many occasions, more abundant than gastropods in sedimentary environments (DENADAI AND AMARAL, 1999; RUEDA, FERNÁNDEZ-CASADO, SALAS AND GOFAS, 2001; MOREIRA *ET AL.*, 2005). In this paper, we present a list of gastropod species found during the sampling programmes developed by the group of Adaptaciones de Animales Marinos from the University of Vigo between 1995 and 1997 in the Ensenada de Baiona. The description of gastropod assemblages in the soft bottoms of the inlet is also provided and relates them to sediment characteristics and other environmental features. This work is part of a baseline study on the benthic assemblages from subtidal sediments of the Ensenada de Baiona; temporal dynamics of gastropod assemblages will be described elsewhere.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

The Ensenada de Baiona is located on the southern margin of the mouth of the Ría de Vigo, between 42° 07' N - 42° 09' N and 08° 51' W - 08° 49' W (Fig. 1). Salinity ranges from 32‰ in winter to 35‰ in summer in the outer area, and from 28‰ to 35‰ in the harbour area. The northern and eastern margins of the inlet are bordered by sandy beaches, while the western outer margin is exposed to oceanic swell and winter winds (ALEJO, AUSTIN, FRANCÉS AND VILAS, 1999); the harbour jetty provides

Figure 1. Location of the Ensenada de Baiona and sampling sites. Sites are grouped according to Cluster and Simprof analysis.

Figura 1. Localización de la ensenada de Baiona y de los puntos de muestreo. Los puntos de muestreo se agrupan en función de los resultados de los análisis Cluster y Simprof.

shelter to the southern area around the harbour of Baiona. Most of its soft bottoms are sandy; the distribution of sediments follows a gradient in grain size (ALEJO *ET AL.*, 1999; MOREIRA *ET AL.*, 2005). Sediments of the outer mouth of the inlet are composed of gravel and coarse sand; in the central area the dominant fractions are medium and fine sand, while sediments in northern and eastern margins are constituted mostly by fine and very fine sand (MOREIRA *ET AL.*, 2005). Sediments in the harbour area range from sandy mud to mud with percentages of silt/clay of up to 90%.

Sampling

In order to study diversity and distribution of gastropods, quantitative sampling was done at the Ensenada de Baiona in December 1995 at 21 subtidal sandy

sites (Table I). Four of these sites were further studied with a monthly periodicity between February 1996 and February 1997 (results will be published in a forthcoming paper). Five replicates were taken at each site using a van Veen grab with a sampling area of 0.056 m² thus covering a total area of 0.28 m² on each site. Samples were sieved through a 0.5 mm mesh and fixed in 10% buffered formalin for later sorting and identification of the fauna. An additional sediment sample was taken at each site to determine granulometric composition, median grain size (Q₅₀), sorting coefficient (S₀), carbonates (%) and total organic matter (TOM, %). The following sedimentary fractions were considered: gravel (GR, > 2 mm), very coarse sand (VCS, 2-1 mm), coarse sand (CS, 1-0.5 mm), medium sand (MS, 0.5-0.25 mm), fine sand (FS, 0.25-0.125 mm), very fine sand (VFS,

Table I. Coordinates and physical characteristics of the sampling sites in the Ensenada de Baiona. Q_{50} , median grain size; $CO_3^{=}$, carbonate content; TOM, total organic matter content.

Tabla I. Coordenadas y características físicas de los puntos de muestreo en la ensenada de Baiona. Q_{50} , mediana del tamaño de grano; $CO_3^{=}$, contenido en carbonatos; TOM, materia orgánica total.

Site	Position (N)	Position (W)	Depth (m)	Gravel (%)	Sand (%)	Silt/Clay (%)	Q_{50} (mm)	Sedimentary type	Sorting	$CO_3^{=}$ (%)	TOM (%)
1	42°08'50"N	08°50'52"W	7	94.23	5.74	0.03	5.00	Gravel	Moderate	24.26	1.48
2	42°08'50"N	08°50'15"W	7	3.52	89.96	6.52	0.13	Muddy sand	Moderate	32.39	1.91
3	42°08'50"N	08°49'44"W	4	0.01	87.19	12.80	0.09	Muddy sand	Moderately well sorted	29.67	2.27
4	42°08'30"N	08°50'52"W	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	42°08'30"N	08°50'15"W	11	0.15	88.40	11.45	0.09	Muddy sand	Moderately well sorted	34.37	1.70
6	42°08'30"N	08°49'44"W	7	0.09	90.66	9.25	0.09	Muddy sand	Moderately well sorted	37.59	2.10
7	42°08'30"N	08°49'13"W	3	0.04	96.44	3.53	0.15	Fine sand	Moderate	48.33	2.05
8	42°08'10"N	08°50'52"W	12	10.29	88.40	1.31	0.83	Coarse sand	Moderate	68.94	1.48
9	42°08'10"N	08°50'15"W	10	1.24	95.70	3.06	0.35	Medium sand	Moderate	82.67	2.28
10	42°08'10"N	08°49'44"W	8	5.84	88.94	5.22	0.14	Muddy sand	Moderate	49.13	2.20
11	42°08'10"N	08°49'13"W	3	0.18	84.28	15.54	0.10	Muddy sand	Moderately well sorted	44.20	2.58
12	42°07'50"N	08°50'52"W	9	8.27	91.71	0.03	0.90	Coarse sand	Moderate	61.31	1.32
13	42°07'50"N	08°50'15"W	8	0.44	96.47	3.09	0.34	Medium sand	Moderate	79.68	2.07
14	42°07'50"N	08°49'44"W	9	1.14	95.70	3.16	0.31	Medium sand	Moderate	80.35	2.18
15	42°07'50"N	08°49'13"W	4	0.03	95.83	4.14	0.14	Fine sand	Moderate	45.00	2.32
16	42°07'30"N	08°50'45"W	4	0.04	9.85	90.11	0.02	Mud	Poor	5.81	12.05
17	42°07'30"N	08°50'15"W	7	9.63	84.18	6.19	0.23	Muddy sand	Moderate	72.91	3.18
18	42°07'30"N	08°49'44"W	8	2.11	94.08	3.82	0.23	Fine sand	Moderate	75.33	2.48
19	42°07'19"N	08°50'45"W	2	2.53	22.95	74.52	0.02	Mud	Poor	7.11	8.45
20	42°07'10"N	08°50'15"W	3	0.17	21.66	78.17	0.02	Mud	Poor	6.85	7.28
21	42°07'10"N	08°49'44"W	3	0.19	50.61	49.20	0.06	Sandy mud	Poor	4.36	2.82

0.125-0.063 mm), and silt/clay (< 0.063 mm). Sedimentary types were characterized according to JUNOY AND VIÉITEZ (1989). Carbonate content (%) was estimated by treating of the sample with hydrochloric acid. The total organic matter content (TOM, %) was estimated from the weight loss on combustion at 450°C for 4 hours.

Data analyses

The total abundance (N), number of species (S), the Shannon-Wiener diversity index (H' , \log_2) and Pielou's evenness (J)

were calculated for each site. Gastropod assemblages were determined through non-parametric multivariate techniques (FIELD, CLARKE AND WARWICK, 1982), using the Primer 6 software package (CLARKE AND GORLEY, 2006). Similarities between samples were determined based on the abundance data of species. These data were transformed prior to the analyses by applying square root in order to down-weight the contribution of the most abundant species. Data were previously averaged across the five replicates for each site thus obtaining a centroid. From the simi-

Figure 2. Dendrogram of classification of sampling sites according to values of Bray-Curtis similarity index calculated on data of species abundance. Groups of sites (A-E) were determined according to Simprof results.

Figura 2. Dendrograma de clasificación de los puntos de muestreo en función del índice de similitud de Bray-Curtis calculado según los datos de abundancia de las especies. Las agrupaciones de los puntos de muestreo (A-E) fueron determinadas según el análisis Simprof.

larity matrix, a classification of the sampling sites was done by Cluster analysis based on the group-average sorting algorithm, obtaining a dendrogram. Clusters of sites determined as statistically significant by profile test Simprof ($p < 0.05$) were considered as having a similar gastropod composition. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) was used to produce a visual representation of the ordination of centroids. Cluster analysis was also done to check for species affinities (inverse analysis) based on the abundance data of the numerically dominant species, i.e. those whose abundance is $\geq 1\%$ of the total abundance.

The possible relationship between gastropod fauna and the measured environmental variables was explored using the Bio-Env procedure (Primer). All variables expressed in percentages were previously transformed by $\log(x+1)$. The following variables were considered in these analyses: TOM, granulometric fractions (GR, CS, MS, FS, VFS), median

grain size, sorting coefficient, skewness, kurtosis, temperature and depth, while carbonates, VCS, silt/clay and pH were excluded due to their high correlation with other variables ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.01$). Sites 1 and 4 were discarded for Bio-Env analysis because of their stony nature, which could make interpretation of the analyses difficult, and insufficient sediment sample from site 4.

RESULTS

Cartography of subtidal sediments in 1995 yielded a total of 1631 specimens belonging to 47 species (Table II). 14 additional species were found during the temporal study (from February 1996 to February 1997), bringing the total number of species up to 61. The richest family in number of species was Pyramidellidae (10) and the best represented in number of individuals was Caecidae (23.8% of total abundance; Table III). About half of the

Table II. Systematic list of all gastropod species found in the Ensenada de Baiona during the cartography (December 1995) and the temporal study (*, February 1996-February 1997).

Tabla II. Lista sistemática de todas las especies de gasterópodos encontradas en la ensenada de Baiona durante el estudio cartográfico (Diciembre 1995) y temporal (*, Febrero 1996-Febrero 1997).

Subclass PROSOBRANCHIA	Family Conidae Fleming, 1822
Family Patellidae Rafinesque, 1815	<i>Bela nebula</i> (Montagu, 1803)
<i>Ansates pellucida</i> (Linneo, 1758)	<i>Mangelia attenuata</i> (Montagu, 1803)
Family Acmaeidae Carpenter, 1857	<i>Mangelia coerctata</i> (Forbes, 1840)
<i>Tectura virginea</i> (Müller, 1776)	Family Omalogyridae Sars, 1878
Family Fissurellidae Fleming, 1822	<i>Omalogyra atomus</i> (Philippi, 1841)
<i>Emarginula rosea</i> Bell, 1824	Family Pyramidellidae Gray, 1840
<i>Puncturella noachina</i> (Linneo, 1771)	<i>Chrysalida decussata</i> (Montagu, 1803)
Family Trochidae Rafinesque, 1815	<i>Chrysalida fenestrata</i> (Jeffreys, 1848)
<i>Gibbula cineraria</i> (Linneo, 1758)	<i>Chrysalida indistincta</i> (Montagu, 1808)
<i>Gibbula magus</i> (Linneo, 1758)	<i>Chrysalida terebellum</i> (Philippi, 1844)
<i>Gibbula tumida</i> (Montagu, 1803)	<i>Eulimella acicula</i> (Philippi, 1836)
<i>Jujubinus exasperatus</i> (Pennant, 1777)	<i>Odostomia conoidea</i> (Brocchi, 1814)
Family Phasianellidae Swainson, 1840	<i>Odostomia eulimoides</i> Hanley, 1844
<i>Tricolia pullus</i> (Linneo, 1758)	<i>Odostomia scalaris</i> MacGillivray 1843
Family Cerithiidae Fleming, 1822	<i>Odostomia unidentata</i> (Montagu, 1803)
<i>Bittium reticulatum</i> (da Costa, 1778)	* <i>Ondina diaphana</i> (Jeffreys, 1848)
Family Turritellidae Woodward, 1851	* <i>Turbonilla lactea</i> (Linneo, 1758)
<i>Turritella communis</i> Risso, 1826	<i>Turbonilla pusilla</i> (Philippi, 1844)
Family Eulimidae H. Adams & A. Adams, 1853	Family Murchisonellidae Casey, 1905
<i>Melanella alba</i> (da Costa, 1778)	<i>Ebala nitidissima</i> (Montagu, 1803)
Family Rissoidae Gray, 1847	Subclass OPISTHOBRANCHIA
<i>Alvania beani</i> (Hanley in Thorpe, 1844)	Family Acteonidae d'Orbigny, 1835
<i>Manzonina crassa</i> (Kanmacher, 1798)	<i>Acteon tornatilis</i> (Linneo, 1758)
<i>Onoba semicostata</i> (Montagu, 1803)	Family Diaphanidae Odhner, 1814
* <i>Pusillina inconspicua</i> (Alder, 1844)	* <i>Diaphana minuta</i> Brown, 1827
* <i>Rissoa guerinii</i> Récluz, 1843	Family Retusidae Thiele, 1925
<i>Rissoa lilacina</i> Récluz, 1843	<i>Cylichnina umbilicata</i> (Montagu, 1803)
<i>Rissoa parva</i> (da Costa, 1778)	<i>Retusa mammillata</i> (Phillipi, 1836)
Family Caecidae Gray, 1850	* <i>Retusa obtusa</i> (Montagu, 1803)
* <i>Caecum glabrum</i> (Montagu, 1803)	<i>Retusa truncatula</i> (Bruguière, 1792)
<i>Caecum trachea</i> (Montagu, 1803)	<i>Volvulella acuminata</i> (Bruguière, 1792)
Family Calyptraeidae Blainville, 1824	Family Philinidae Gray, 1850
<i>Calyptraea chinensis</i> (Linneo, 1758)	<i>Philina aperta</i> (Linneo, 1767)
* <i>Crepidula fornicata</i> (Linneo, 1758)	<i>Philina punctata</i> (Adams, 1800)
Family Naticidae Gray, 1840	<i>Philina scabra</i> (Müller, 1784)
<i>Euspira pulchella</i> (Risso, 1826)	Family Cylichnidae Lovèn, 1846
Family Muricidae Rafinesque, 1815	<i>Cylichna cylindracea</i> (Pennant, 1777)
<i>Ocenebra erinaceus</i> (Linneo, 1758)	Family Limapontiidae Gray, 1847
Family Nassariidae Iredale, 1916	* <i>Limapontia depressa</i> Alder & Hancock, 1862
<i>Nassarius incrassatus</i> (Ström, 1768)	Family Akeridae Odhner, 1922
<i>Nassarius pygmaeus</i> (Lamarck, 1822)	* <i>Akera bullata</i> Müller, 1776
<i>Nassarius reticulatus</i> (Linneo, 1758)	Family Dorididae Rafinesque, 1815
	<i>Doris verrucosa</i> Linneo, 1758

Figure 3. nMDS ordination of sampling sites showing groups determined by Cluster and Simprof analysis.

Figura 3. Ordenación nMDS de los puntos de muestreo indicando los grupos determinados por los análisis Cluster y Simprof.

species found were represented by less than 10 individuals each. The best represented taxa in the inlet (present in at least 50% of the sampling sites) were the nassariid, *Nassarius reticulatus* (Linneo, 1758), and the naticid, *Euspira pulchella* (Risso, 1826). The total number of species per site ranged from 1-2 (sites 3, 11 and 16; Table IV) to 17-19 (sites 4, 17-18). Maximal total gastropod densities were found at sites 18, 4 and 21 (>700 ind. m^{-2}) and the lowest ones at sites 3, 11 and 16 (<40 ind. m^{-2}). The highest values of diversity (H') were recorded at sites 17 and 18 ($H' > 3.00$ bits); those sites also showed a high evenness ($J > 0.70$). Diversity was smaller than 1.0 bits in sites 3, 6, 11, 16 and 20; the lowest values of evenness were found at sites 3 and 20 ($J < 0.40$).

Gastropod assemblages

The dendrogram obtained by Cluster analysis showed five major groups of sites (Fig. 2): group A (sites 8,

9, 12, 13, 14; coarse and medium sand), group B (st. 1 and 4, gravel), group C (st. 16, 19, 20 and 21; sandy mud and mud), group D (st. 3, 6, 7, 11 and 15; fine sand sites at the margins of the inlet) and E (st. 2, 5, 10, 17 and 18; fine sand sites at the centre of the inlet). These groups were found to have an internal structure according to the Simprof test ($p < 0.05$). The graphic representation of the nMDS analysis showed an ordination of sites which agrees with dendrogram groups and distribution of sedimentary types (Fig. 3). Group A was located in the outer and central parts of the inlet and was characterized by *Caecum trachea* (Montagu, 1803), *Cylichnina umbilicata* (Montagu, 1803) and *Philine* spp. Group B was composed of sites located in the northern outer area and was numerically dominated by *Tectura virginea* (Müller, 1776), *Calyptrea chinensis* (Linneo, 1758) and *Gibbula* spp. Sites of group C were situated around the

Table III. Abundance of dominant species (abundance $\geq 1\%$ of total abundance) in each sampling site expressed as individuals per m².

Sampling site	8	9	12	13	14	1	4	16	19	20	21
Dendrogram group	A	A	A	A	A	B	B	C	C	C	C
Species											
<i>Caecum trachea</i>	160.7	482.1	78.6	210.7	410.7	-	3.6	-	-	-	-
<i>Bittium reticulatum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17.9	17.9	235.7	628.6
<i>Cylichna umbilicata</i>	-	35.7	-	110.7	135.7	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Nassarius reticulatus</i>	-	-	-	-	7.1	-	17.9	-	3.6	17.9	3.6
<i>Tectura virginea</i>	-	-	-	-	-	39.3	317.9	-	-	-	-
<i>Gibbula tumida</i>	-	-	3.6	-	25.0	75.0	89.3	-	3.6	-	-
<i>Retusa truncatula</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.6	7.1	-	135.7
<i>Gibbula cineraria</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	92.9	-	-	-	-
<i>Calyptrea chinensis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	96.4	-	-	-	-
<i>Chrysalida terebellum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50.0
<i>Philine punctata</i>	-	107.1	-	-	7.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Euspira pulchella</i>	14.3	-	7.1	7.1	10.7	7.1	7.1	-	-	-	-
<i>Philine aperta</i>	32.1	3.6	28.6	3.6	10.7	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Bela nebula</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Cylichna cylindracea</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Nassarius pygmaeus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

harbour of Baiona; the group was characterized by a small total number of species (10); *Bittium reticulatum* (da Costa, 1778) was the dominant species followed by *Retusa truncatula* (Bruguère, 1792). Group D was distributed along the margins of the inlet; this group was the poorest in terms of number of species and individuals. Group E was composed of fine sand sites located in the central area and was characterized by the highest total number of species (29); *N. reticulatus* and *C. umbilicata* were the numerically dominant species.

According to Simper analysis, dissimilarities between groups A (coarser sandy sediments) and B (gravel) were determined by *C. trachea*, *T. virginea*, *Gibbula tumida* (Montagu, 1803), *C. umbilicata* and *Philine aperta* (Linneo, 1767) (up to 50% of total dissimilarity); the species that most contributed to dissimilarities between A and D (fine-sand sites at the margins of the inlet) were *C. trachea*, *C. umbilicata* and *N. reticulatus* (up to 55% of dissimilarity) and

between A and E (fine-sand sites at the central area of the inlet) were the same aforementioned species together with *P. aperta* and *Cylichna cylindracea* (Pennant, 1777) (up to 50% of dissimilarity). Most of the total dissimilarity (up to 50%) between groups D and E were due to *C. umbilicata*, *N. reticulatus*, *C. cylindracea*, *R. truncatula*, *Nassarius pygmaeus* (Lamarck, 1822), *E. pulchella* and *Bela nebula* (Montagu, 1803); those species were more abundant in group E than in group D. The species *B. reticulatum* and *N. reticulatus* were responsible for up to 50% dissimilarity between groups C (mud sites) and D while *B. reticulatum*, *reticulatus* *C. umbilicata*, *E. pulchella* and *C. cylindracea* were the species most contributing to total dissimilarity between groups C and E (up to 50%).

Species affinities

The dendrogram obtained by inverse analysis done on the abundance data of the species considered as dominant in each site showed four main groups at a 40% similarity level (Fig. 4).

Tabla III. Abundancia de las especies dominantes (abundancia $\geq 1\%$ de la abundancia total) en cada punto de muestreo expresada como individuos por m^2 .

Sampling site	3	6	7	11	15	2	5	10	17	18
Dendrogram group	D	D	D	D	D	E	E	E	E	E
Species										
<i>Caecum trachea</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.6	35.7
<i>Bittium reticulatum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	7.1	-	-	-	-
<i>Cylichna umbilicata</i>	-	-	-	3.6	-	110.7	-	17.9	-	239.3
<i>Nassarius reticulatus</i>	10.7	28.6	21.4	17.9	32.1	53.6	25.0	42.9	128.6	196.4
<i>Tectura virginea</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.6
<i>Gibbula tumida</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Retusa truncatula</i>	-	-	-	-	-	7.1	7.1	7.1	14.3	7.1
<i>Gibbula cineraria</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.6	14.3	46.4
<i>Calyptrea chinensis</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10.7	28.6
<i>Chrysallida terebellum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	25.0	-	-	25.0	17.9
<i>Philine punctata</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.6
<i>Euspira pulchella</i>	-	3.6	-	-	3.6	7.1	14.3	3.6	10.7	17.9
<i>Philine aperta</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Bela nebula</i>	-	3.6	-	-	7.1	10.7	-	3.6	25.0	25.0
<i>Cylichna cylindracea</i>	-	-	-	-	-	3.6	7.1	3.6	21.4	39.3
<i>Nassarius pygmaeus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	7.1	10.7	-	28.6	25.0

Group 1 included species mostly found at sites dominated by coarser sandy fractions (site group A), i.e. *C. trachea*, *Philine aperta* and *P. punctata* (Adams, 1800). Group 2 was composed of species whose higher abundance was found in gravelly sites (site group B); those species were *T. virginea*, *C. chinensis*, *Gibbula cineraria* (Linneo, 1758) and *G. tumida*. Group 3 was composed of *B. reticulatum*, *R. truncatula* and *Chrysallida terebellum* (Philippi, 1844); those species were present in fine-sand and mud sites but were more abundant in the latter sediments. Group 4 comprised the largest group of species, which were mainly found in site groups D and E; group 4 included species that were widespread across fine-sand sites such as *N. reticulatus*, *E. pulchella* and *C. umbilicata*.

Gastropod fauna and environmental variables

The Bio-Env procedure showed that a number of combinations of the selected environmental variables had

high correlations with abundance data of gastropod species through the Spearman rank correlation coefficient ($p > 0.70$ in many cases). The best combinations of variables were those composed of organic matter, sorting coefficient, coarse sand, medium sand, very fine sand and skewness. The median grain size was the variable that alone showed the highest correlation ($p = 0.57$), followed by very fine sand ($p = 0.51$). The nMDS ordination of sites with superimposed values of the mentioned variables showed that sites appeared distributed from left to right following decreasing values of median grain size; sites with greater content in very fine sand were located in the central part of the graphic representation (Fig. 5).

DISCUSSION

Quantitative sampling showed that the soft-bottom gastropod fauna from the Ensenada de Baiona is rich and diverse in number of species (61) and its

Table IV. Total number of species per 0.28 m² (S), total abundance per m² (N), Shannon-Wiener's diversity index (H', log₂) and Pielou's evenness (J) for each sampling site. The group to which each sampling site belongs according to multivariate analyses is also indicated.

Tabla IV. Número total de especies por 0.28 m² (S), abundancia total por m² (N), índice de diversidad de Shannon-Wiener (H', log₂) y equidad de Pielou (J) para cada punto de muestreo. Se indica el grupo al que pertenece cada punto de muestreo de acuerdo con los análisis multivariante.

Sampling site	Group	S	N	H' (log ₂)	J'
8	A	4	211	1.07	0.54
9	A	7	643	1.17	0.42
12	A	7	132	1.80	0.64
13	A	5	364	1.46	0.63
14	A	13	639	1.75	0.47
1	B	9	154	2.16	0.68
4	B	17	750	2.75	0.67
16	C	2	21	0.65	0.65
19	C	5	36	1.96	0.84
20	C	3	257	0.47	0.30
21	C	7	861	1.30	0.46
3	D	1	11	0.00	0.00
6	D	3	36	0.92	0.58
7	D	4	36	1.57	0.79
11	D	2	21	0.65	0.65
15	D	5	71	1.98	0.85
2	E	11	246	2.51	0.72
5	E	6	68	2.33	0.90
10	E	11	104	2.74	0.79
17	E	18	436	3.46	0.83
18	E	19	729	3.03	0.71

composition is similar to those reported from other areas in the northern Iberian Peninsula (e. g. MARTÍNEZ AND ADARAGA, 2003; TRONCOSO, MOREIRA AND URGORRI, 2005; LOURIDO, GESTOSO AND TRONCOSO, 2006). In addition, the total number of species is within the same range as those recorded in studies done in other Galician rias which covered similar types of sediments. For example, TRONCOSO, PARAPAR AND URGORRI (1993) and GARMENDIA, SÁNCHEZ-MATA AND MORA (1998) reported, respectively, 62 and 66 species from the Ría de Ares-Betanzos, and LOURIDO *ET AL.* (2006) found 60 species at the Ría de Aldán. Although the aforementioned rias are much larger than the Ensenada de Baiona they share with the latter a similar gastropod diversity. Those rias

are characterized by having a large variety of sedimentary types, which are usually distributed following a gradient in grain size, i.e. coarser sediments appear at the mouth of the rias and finer sediments towards the internal areas (TRONCOSO & URGORRI, 1993; LOURIDO *ET AL.*, 2006). In general, this sedimentary diversity usually translates into more diverse benthic faunas than those which appear in areas where sediments are more homogeneous. Thus, many of the southern rias (Rías Baixas) which are dominated by muddy sediments with high contents of organic matter have poorer gastropod assemblages. For instance, LÓPEZ-JAMAR (1981) reported 7 species of gastropods from the Ría de Muros and 8 species from the Ría de Pontevedra (LÓPEZ-JAMAR, 1978) while

Figure 4. Dendrogram of classification of dominant species according to values of Bray-Curtis similarity index calculated on data of species abundance.

Figura 4. Dendrograma de clasificación de las especies dominantes en función del índice de similitud de Bray-Curtis calculado según los datos de abundancia de las especies.

CACABELOS, QUINTAS AND TRONCOSO (2008) found 34 species at the Ensenada de San Simón (Ría de Vigo).

Multivariate analyses showed that distribution and composition of gastropod assemblages are strongly related to the granulometric composition and the median grain size of the sediment. In fact, the same patterns have also been found for distribution of polychaetes and peracarid crustaceans in the same area (MOREIRA, QUINTAS AND TRONCOSO, 2006; MOREIRA, LOURIDO AND TRONCOSO, 2008). The distribution of sediments in the Ensenada de Baiona is, in turn, conditioned by patterns of local hydrodynamism (ALEJO AND VILAS, 1987; ALEJO ET AL., 1999). Indeed, hydrodynamism is regarded as the 'superparameter' acting as a source of disturbance for benthos at large scales (BREY, 1991); this superparameter affects other abiotic factors which also have a great influence on benthic assemblages, such as granulometric composition and

availability of organic matter (MANCINELLI, FAZI AND ROSSI, 1998; ELÍAS, PALACIOS, RIVERO AND VALLARINO, 2005).

Sampling sites with a high content of the gravel fraction (group of sites B) have a gastropod fauna which is dominated by epifaunal species such as *Calyptraea chinensis*, trochids and limpets (Patellidae, Fissurellidae). These species can appear in numbers on sediments when stones or bioclastic components such as dead shells of other molluscs are present (RUEDA AND SALAS, 2003); those constitute the "hard" substrata in an otherwise soft bottom. Furthermore, some of those species, namely *Gibbula cineraria* and *C. chinensis*, were also found in numbers in fine-sand sites (group E, sites 17-18) because large shells of both *Lutraria* spp. and venerid bivalves were on the surface of the sediment. The gastropod assemblage from coarser sandy sediments was numerically dominated by *Caecum trachea*. High

Figure 5. nMDS ordination of sampling sites with values of some abiotic variables superimposed. A, median grain size; B, very fine sand. Stress: 0.13.

Figura 5. Ordenación nMDS de los puntos de muestreo mostrando los valores de algunas variables abióticas superimpuestas. A, mediana del tamaño de grano; B, arena muy fina. Estrés: 0,13.

numbers of this species have also been reported from similar sediments in the Ría de Ares-Betanzos (TRONCOSO ET AL., 2005) and the Ría de Aldán (LOURIDO ET AL., 2006), this species being an important component in terms of abundance of the whole benthic assemblage. On the other hand, *Nassarius reticulatus* was found in a range of sediments, from gravel to mud, being the dominant gastropod in the fine-sand sediments. This is a common species in subtidal fine sediments in European Atlantic coasts in general (BARROSO, MOREIRA AND RICHARDSON, 2005), and in the Galician rias in particular (OLABARRIA, TRONCOSO AND URGORRI, 1998; TRONCOSO ET AL., 2005). This species migrates from intertidal areas to subtidal areas in autumn (TALLMARK, 1980), which might explain its wide distribution through the inlet at the time of sampling, being present both in shallow and deeper sediments. Another abundant species in medium- and fine-sand sediments was the bullomorpha *Cylichnina umbilicata*, which has scarcely been reported in the literature as a numerically dominant species in gastropod assemblages. This fact can be related to its small size (about 4 mm) and the extended use of sieving meshes greater than 500 μm , which can lead to an underestimation of its abundance. In the Ensenada de Baiona, this species appears mostly in sandy sediments with a great content of

the medium-sand fraction while the related species *Retusa truncatula* replaces the former in muddier sandy sediments. On the contrary, *R. truncatula* has frequently been found in sandy sediments in other rias, such as happens in the Ría de Ferrol (OLABARRIA ET AL., 1998). The other representative of the Bullomorpha which has often been recorded from sandy and muddy sediments in the Galician rias is *Cylichna cylindracea* (GARMENDIA ET AL., 1998; LOURIDO ET AL., 2006). Nevertheless, in the Ensenada de Baiona this species was not so abundant as the other two aforementioned species and was only found in some sandy sites. Pyramidellidae was the family best represented in number of species at the Ensenada de Baiona. Nevertheless, many of the species were found in small numbers. Pyramidellids are ectoparasites of many marine invertebrates and tend to show specificity for their hosts (FRETTER AND GRAHAM, 1949). On soft-bottoms, polychaetes and bivalves are common hosts. The most abundant species at the Ensenada de Baiona was *Chrysallida terebellum*, which appeared in fine-sand sites and in muddy sand. At those sites, 'sedentary' polychaetes were abundant (MOREIRA ET AL., 2006) which might favour the presence of *C. terebellum* in numbers there.

The smallest values for number of species and diversity were found at several shallow fine-sand sites close to

sandy beaches and at muddy sediments around the harbour of Baiona. In the first case, those sites are subjected to strong hydrodynamism all the year round, and particularly during winter (pers. obs.) This hydrodynamism might create an unstable sedimentary environment which is limitant for the establishment of many species, therefore resulting in poor gastropod assemblages (NETTO, ATTRILL AND WARWICK, 1999). This pattern has also been detected for polychaetes and peracarid crustaceans in the same sampling sites (MOREIRA *ET AL.*, 2006, 2008). On the other hand, sediments around the harbour of Baiona have turned from sandy to muddy in the last years and now support a poor gastropod assemblage, mostly at sites 16 and 19. Thus, ALEJO AND VILAS (1987) reported a dominance of the fine and very fine sand fractions in the sediment composition during the 1980's whereas we found percentages of silt-clay ranging from 74-90% in 1995. This increase in content of silt-clay might be due to the construction of the jetty which provides shelter against oceanic swell for the Baiona harbour. The presence of that jetty has indeed altered the hydrodynamic conditions in this area (ALEJO AND VILAS, 1987), thus allowing a greater rate of sedimentation of finer particles on the sheltered areas of the

harbour. Although the quantitative data on the benthic fauna inhabiting those sediments previous to the construction of the jetty are not available, it can be suspected that this change in sedimentary composition has led to an impoverishment in the composition of the benthic assemblage as a whole, including its gastropod fauna. These and other similar alterations are frequent nowadays in coastal areas because of the increase of the human population living on the coast (CHAPMAN, 2006); this usually translates into a loss of local biodiversity and changes in the species composition of the assemblage. To prevent this, taking some simple measures such as building channels under breakwaters and jetties may improve hydrodynamic conditions (GUERRA-GARCÍA AND GARCÍA-GÓMEZ, 2004) and therefore prevent sedimentation in great quantities of both finer particles and organic matter.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALEJO I., AUSTIN W. E. N., FRANCÉS G. AND VILAS F. 1999. Preliminary investigations of the recent Foraminifera of Baiona Bay, N.W. Spain. *Journal of Coastal Research*, 15: 413-427.
- ALEJO I. AND VILAS F. 1987. Dinámica litoral y evolución histórica de la Ensenada de Baiona (Pontevedra). *Thalassas*, 5: 21-32.
- BARROSO C.M., MOREIRA M.H. AND RICHARDSON C.A. 2005. Age and growth of *Nassarius reticulatus* in the Ria de Aveiro, north-west Portugal. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U. K.*, 85: 151-156.
- BOENING D.W. 1999. An evaluation of bivalves as biomonitors of heavy metals pollution in marine waters. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 55: 459-470.
- BREY T. 1991. The relative significance of biological and physical disturbance: an example from intertidal and subtidal sandy bottom communities. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 33: 339-360.
- CACABELOS E., QUINTAS P. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 2008. Spatial distribution of soft-bottom molluscs in the Ensenada de San Simón (NW Spain). *American Malacological Bulletin*, 25: 9-19.
- CASTELLANOS C., HERNÁNDEZ-VEGA S. AND JUNOY J. 2003. Cambios bentónicos en la ría de Foz (Lugo) (noroeste de España) tras la construcción de un espigón. *Boletín del Instituto Español de Oceanografía*, 19: 205-217.

- CHAPMAN M.G. 2006. Intertidal seawalls as habitat for molluscs. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 72: 247-257.
- CLARKE K.R. AND GORLEY R.N. 2006. *PRIMER V6: user manual/tutorial*. PRIMER-E Ltd., Plymouth, U.K.
- DENADAI M.R. AND AMARAL A.C.Z. 1999. A comparative study of intertidal molluscan communities in sandy beaches, Sao Sebastiao Channel, Sao Paulo State, Brazil. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 65: 91-103.
- ELÍAS R., PALACIOS J.R., RIVERO M.S. AND VALLARINO E.A. 2005. Short-term responses to sewage discharge and storms of subtidal sand-bottom macrozoobenthic assemblages off Mar del Plata City, Argentina (SW Atlantic). *Journal of Sea Research*, 53: 231-242.
- FIELD J.G., CLARKE K.R. AND WARWICK R.M. 1982. A practical strategy for analysing multispecies distribution patterns. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 8: 37-52.
- FRETTER V. AND GRAHAM A. 1949. The structure and mode of life of the Pyramidellidae, parasitic opisthobranchs. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U. K.*, 28: 493-532.
- GARMENDIA J.M., SÁNCHEZ-MATA A. AND MORA J. 1998. Inventario de la macrofauna bentónica de sustratos blandos submareales de la Ría de Ares y Betanzos (NO de la Península Ibérica). *Nova Acta Científica Compostelana (Biología)*, 8: 209-231.
- GRAY J.S. 1981. *The ecology of marine sediments*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- GUERRA-GARCÍA J.M. AND GARCÍA-GÓMEZ J.C. 2004. Soft bottom mollusc assemblages and pollution in a harbour with two opposing entrances. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 60: 273-283.
- HIDALGO J.G. 1886. Catálogo de los moluscos recogidos en Bayona de Galicia y lista de las especies marinas que viven en la costa noroeste de España. *Revista del Progreso de Ciencias Exactas, Físicas y Naturales*, 21(7): 373-414.
- JUNOY J. AND VIÉITEZ J.M. 1989. Cartografía de los sedimentos superficiales de la Ría de Foz (Lugo). *Thalassas*, 7: 9-19.
- LÓPEZ-JAMAR E. 1978. Primeros datos sobre la biomasa y la composición del bentos infaunal de la ría de Pontevedra, en relación con el contenido en materia orgánica del sedimento. *Boletín del Instituto Español de Oceanografía*, 4: 57-69.
- LÓPEZ-JAMAR E. 1981. Spatial distribution of the infaunal benthic communities of the Ría de Muros, North-West Spain. *Marine Biology*, 63: 29-37.
- LÓPEZ-JAMAR E., GONZÁLEZ G. AND MEJUTO J. 1986. Temporal changes of community structure and biomass in two subtidal macroinfaunal assemblages in La Coruña bay, NW Spain. *Hydrobiologia*, 142: 137-150.
- LÓPEZ-JAMAR E. AND MEJUTO J. 1985. Bentos infaunal en la zona submareal de la ría de La Coruña. I. Estructura y distribución espacial de las comunidades. *Boletín del Instituto Español de Oceanografía*, 2(3): 99-109.
- LOURIDO A., GESTOSO L. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 2006. Assemblages of the molluscan fauna in subtidal soft bottoms of the Ría de Aldán (north-western Spain). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U. K.*, 86: 129-140.
- MACANDREW R. 1849. On the Mollusca of Vigo Bay in the Northwest of Spain. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, 2(3): 507-513.
- MANCINELLI G., FAZI S. AND ROSSI L. 1998. Sediment structural properties mediating dominant feeding types patterns in soft-bottom macrobenthos of the Northern Adriatic Sea. *Hydrobiologia*, 367: 211-222.
- MARTÍNEZ J. AND ADARRAGA I. 2003. Estructura y evolución temporal de los sedimentos y de las comunidades bentónicas afectadas por los vertidos de un colector de aguas residuales en San Sebastián (Guipúzcoa) (golfo de Vizcaya). *Boletín del Instituto Español de Oceanografía*, 19: 345-370.
- MORA J. 1982. Consideraciones generales sobre la macrofauna bentónica de la Ría de Arosa. *Oecologia aquatica*, 6: 41-49.
- MOREIRA J., QUINTAS P. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 2005. Distribution of the molluscan fauna in subtidal soft bottoms of the Ensenada de Baiona (NW Spain). *American Malacological Bulletin*, 20: 75-86.
- MOREIRA J., QUINTAS P. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 2006. Spatial distribution of soft-bottom polychaete annelids in the Ensenada de Baiona (Ría de Vigo, Galicia, north-west Spain). *Scientia Marina*, 70 (Supl. 3): 217-224.
- MOREIRA J., LOURIDO A. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 2008. Diversity and distribution of peracarid crustaceans in shallow subtidal soft bottoms at the Ensenada de Baiona (Galicia, N.W. Spain). *Crustaceana*, 81: 1069-1089.
- NETTO S.A., ATTRILL M.J. AND WARWICK R.M. 1999. The effect of a natural water-movement related disturbance on the structure of meiofauna and macrofauna communities in the intertidal sand flat of Rocas Atoll (NE, Brazil). *Journal of Sea Research*, 42: 291-302.
- OLABARRIA C., URGORRI V. AND TRONCOSO J.S. 1998. An analysis of the community structure of subtidal and intertidal benthic mollusks of the Inlet of Baño (Ría de Ferrol) (northwestern Spain). *American Malacological Bulletin*, 14: 103-120.
- ROLÁN E. 1983. Moluscos de la Ría de Vigo I. Gasterópodos. *Thalassas*, anexo 1: 1-383.
- ROLÁN E., OTERO J. AND ROLÁN-ÁLVAREZ E. 1989. Moluscos de la Ría de Vigo II. *Thalassas*, anexo 2: 1-276.

- RUEDA J.L., FERNÁNDEZ-CASADO M., SALAS C. AND GOFAS S. 2001. Seasonality in a taxocoenosis of molluscs from soft bottoms in the Bay of Cádiz (southern Spain). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the U. K.*, 81: 903-912.
- RUEDA J. AND SALAS C. 2003. Temporal dynamics of molluscan assemblages from soft and bioclastic bottoms in the Strait of Gibraltar. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine*, 44: 237-248.
- STUBBLEFIELD W.L., PERMENTER R.W. AND SWIFT D.J.P. 1977. Time and space variation in the surficial sediments of the New York Bight apex. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 5: 597-607.
- TALLMARK B. 1980. Population dynamics of *Nassarius reticulatus* (Gastropoda, Prosobranchia) in Gullmar Fjord, Sweden. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 3: 51-62.
- TRONCOSO J.S., MOREIRA J. AND URGORRI V. 2005. Soft-bottom mollusc assemblages in the Ría de Ares-Betanzos (Galicia, NW Spain). *Iberus*, 23: 25-38.
- TRONCOSO J.S., PARAPAR J. AND URGORRI V. 1993. Cartografía de los moluscos infralitorales de sustratos blandos de la ría de Ares y Betanzos (Galicia, NO de España). *Publicaciones Especiales del Instituto Español de Oceanografía*, 11: 131-137.
- TRONCOSO J.S. AND URGORRI V. 1993. Datos sedimentológicos y macrofauna de los fondos infralitorales de sustrato blando de la Ría de Ares y Betanzos. *Nova Acta Científica Compostelana (Biología)*, 4: 153-166.
- UNDERWOOD A.J. 1992. Beyond BACI: the detection of environmental impacts on populations in the real, but variable world. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*, 161: 145-178.
- WILDISH D.J. 1977. Factors controlling marine and estuarine sublittoral macrofauna. *Helgoländer wissenschaftliche Meeresuntersuchungen*, 30: 445-454.
- WILSON, W. H. 1991. Competition and predation in marine soft-sediment communities. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 21: 221-241.

